

G'OVAK MUHITLARDA MODDA KO'CHIRILISHI TENGLAMASI MANBA HADINI
TIKLASH TESKARI MASALASINI SONLI YECHISH.

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolani yozishimdan maqsad axborot texnologiyalarida xususiy hosilali differensial tenglama uchun chegaraviy masalalarda aniqlovchi tenglama, hisoblash sohasi, chegaraviy va boshlang'ich shartlarni berish bilan tavsiflanadi. Shu sababli teskari masalalarni koeffitsientli, geometrik, chegaraviy va evolyutsion teskari masalalarga bo'ladi. Bu dasturning afzalligi shundaki, simvollar soni cheklanmangan, hamda qaysi tilga o'girishni dasturni o'zi aniqlaydi.*

Kalit so'z: *Identifikatsiya, approksimatsiya, parabolik tenglama, differensial tenglama, chegaraviy masala, aktiv g'ovaklik, joriy konsentratsiya, sizish tezligi, diffuziya koeffitsiyenti, manba hadi, koordinata, - vaqt, g'ovak qatlam uzunligi, jarayonning davomiyligi.*

Xususiy hosilali differensial tenglama uchun chegaraviy masalalarda aniqlovchi tenglama, hisoblash sohasi, chegaraviy va boshlang'ich shartlarni berish bilan tavsiflanadi. Shu sababli teskari masalalarni koeffitsientli, geometrik, chegaraviy va evolyutsion teskari masalalarga bo'lish mumkin.

Umumiy metodologik nuqtai nazardan, to'g'ri masalalar deb sabablari berilgan va izlanayotgan kattaliklar oqibat bo'lgan masalalarni aytish mumkin. Bunday farazga ko'ra oqibatlari ma'lum bo'lgan va sabablari noma'lum bo'lgan masalalarni teskari masalalar desak bo'ladi. Teskari masalalar nokorrekt masalalar hisoblanadi. Teskari masalalar bo'yicha nazariy va amaliy masalalarni [1-6] adabiyotlarda batafsil yoritilgan. Ko'pincha bizda kirill yoki lotin alifbosidagi matnlarni kirilldan-lotinga, lotindan-kirillga o'girishga ehtiyoj bo'ladi. Ushbu kiril lotin, lotin kiril onlayn translit dasturi o'zbek tilidagi har qanday matnlarni hech qanday muammosiz hal qilishingizda sizga yordam beradi. Bu dasturning afzalligi shundaki, simvollar soni cheklanmangan, hamda qaysi tilga o'girishni dasturni o'zi aniqlaydi. Butun bir maqolani yoki matnni birinchi bo'sh katakka qo'ysangiz, bir necha soniyadan so'ng tayyor natijani qo'lga kiritasiz.

Hozircha sinov tartibida ishlayotganligi sababli, natijani tekshirib oling.

Ba'zi bir kamchiliklar bo'lsa administratorga murojat qiling yoki izoh yozib qoldiring.

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \frac{v}{m} \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = \frac{D}{m} \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} + \frac{1}{m} f(x,t), \quad 0 < x < l, \quad 0 < t \leq T, \quad (1)$$

bu yerda m – aktiv g'ovaklik, $c(x,t)$ – joriy konsentratsiya, v – sizish tezligi, D – diffuziya koeffitsiyenti, $f(x,t)$ – manba hadi, x – koordinata, m , t – vaqt, s , l – g'ovak qatlam uzunligi, T – jarayonning davomiyligi, s .

(1) tenglamani quyidagi boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlarda qaraymiz:

$$c(x,0)=0, \quad 0 \leq x \leq l, \quad (2)$$

$$c(0,t)=c_0 = \text{const}, \quad c(l,t)=0, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T. \quad (3)$$

To'g'ri masala (1)-(3) ko'rinishda ifodalanadi.

(1) tenglama o'ng tarafi $f(x,t)$ ni tiklash teskari masalasini qaraymiz. $f(x,t)$

quyidagi ko'rinishda tasvirlansin deb hisoblaymiz

$$\frac{1}{m} f(x,t) = \frac{1}{m} f_0 \eta(t) \psi(x), \quad (4)$$

bu yerda $\psi(x)$ berilgan funksiya, manbaning vaqtdan bog'liq funksiyasi $\eta(t)$ esa noma'lum bo'lsin. Ushbu bog'lanish qandaydir $0 < x^* < l$ ichki nuqtada $c(x,t)$ funksiya bo'yicha qo'shimcha kuzatish orqali tiklansin:

$$c(x^*,t) = \varphi(t). \quad (5)$$

(1)-(5) parabolik tenglamaning o'ng tarafini tiklash bo'yicha sodda masalaga kelamiz.

2. Teskari masalani yechish algoritmi. Tiklash masalasi quyidagi cheklashlarda qaraladi [6, 19]:

1. $\psi(x^*) \neq 0$,
2. $\psi(x)$ – yetarlicha sillqi funksiya ($\psi \in C[0,1]$),
3. Soha chegarasida $\psi(x) = 0$.

Bu yerda asosiy farazlardan biri birinchi farazdir, chunki x^* kuzatish nuqtasida tiklanayotgan manba ta'sir qiladi. Aynan shu narsa qaralayotgan tiklash masalasining korrektiligini ta'minlaydi.

Teskari masala yechimini quyidagi ko'rinishda izlaymiz

$$c(x,t) = \theta(t)\psi(x) + w(x,t), \quad (6)$$

bu yerda

$$\theta(t) = \frac{f_0}{m} \int_0^t \eta(s) ds. \quad (7)$$

(4), (6), (7) ni (1) ga qo'yib, $w(x,t)$ uchun quyidagi tenglamaga kelamiz:

$$\frac{f_0}{m} \eta(t)\psi(x) + \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \frac{v}{m} \theta(t) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{v}{m} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} = \frac{D}{m} \theta(t) \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{D}{m} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{f_0}{m} \eta(t)\psi(x),$$

tenglamani soddalashtirib quyidagiga kelamiz

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \frac{v}{m} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} = \frac{D}{m} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\theta(t)}{m} \left(D \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} - v \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \right). \quad (8)$$

(6) ko'rinishni hisobga olib (5) shartdan $\theta(t)$ noma'lum uchun quyidagi ko'rinishni hosil qilamiz:

$$\theta(t) = \frac{1}{\psi(x^*)} (\varphi(t) - w(x^*, t)). \quad (9)$$

(9) ni (8) ga qo'yib quyidagi parabolik tenglamani hosil qilamiz

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \frac{v}{m} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} = \frac{D}{m} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{1}{m\psi(x^*)} (\varphi(t) - w(x^*, t)) \left(D \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} - v \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \right). \quad (10)$$

$w(x, t)$ uchun chegaraviy shartlar ushbu ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$w(0, t) = c_0, \quad w(l, t) = 0, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T. \quad (11)$$

(7) dan $\theta(t)$ yordamchi funksiya uchun quyidagi kelib chiqadi

$$\theta(0) = 0. \quad (12)$$

Bu esa quyidagi boshlang'ich shartni qo'llash imkonini beradi

$$w(x, 0) = 0, \quad 0 < x < l. \quad (13)$$

Shunday qilib (1)-(5) teskari masala noma'lum manbaning (7), (9) ko'rinishdagi vaqtdan bog'lanishi bo'yicha (10)-(13) tenglama uchun chegaraviy masalaga keltiriladi.

3. Ayirmali masala. Identifikatsiya masalasini sonli yechishning asosiy nuqtalariga to'xtalib o'tamiz. Hisoblash algoritmi (10)-(13) masalani taqribiy yechish algoritmiga tayanadi. Matematik fizikaning bunday noklassik masalalarini sonli yechish algortimlari hozircha yetarlicha ishlab chiqilmagan.

$E = \{0 \leq x \leq l, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ sohada x koordinata va t vaqt bo'yicha tekis to'r kiritamiz [22]:

$$\bar{\Omega} = \Omega_h \times \Omega_\tau = \left\{ (x_i, t_j), x_i = ih, t_j = j\tau, i = 0, 1, \dots, N, j = 0, 1, \dots, M, h = \frac{l}{N}, \tau = \frac{T}{M} \right\}.$$

Soddalik uchun $x = x^*$ kuzatish nuqtasi $i = k$ ichki tugun bilan ustma-ust tushadi deb hisoblaymiz.

(10) tenglamani yechish uchun sof oshkormas ayirmali sxemani qo'llaymiz. (10) ni approksimatsiyalab quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\frac{w_i^{j+1} - w_i^j}{\tau} + \frac{v}{m} \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2h} = \frac{D}{m} \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - 2w_i^{j+1} + w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h^2} + \frac{1}{m\psi_k} (\varphi^{j+1} - w_k^{j+1}) (D(\psi''_{xx})_i - v(\psi'_x)_i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (14)$$

(11), (13) ni approksimatsiyalab quyidagini hosil qilamiz

$$w_0^{j+1} = c_0, \quad w_N^{j+1} = 0, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1, \quad (15)$$

$$w_i^0 = 0, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N. \quad (16)$$

(14)-(16) ayirmali masala yechimidan (9) ga mos ravishda quyidagini aniqlaymiz

$$\theta^{j+1} = \frac{1}{\psi_k} (\varphi^{j+1} - w_k^{j+1}), \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1, \quad (17)$$

bu munosabatni $\theta^0 = 0$ shart bilan to'ldiramiz. (7) munosabatni inobatga olib, izlanayotgan vaqtdan bog'liq bo'lgan o'ng taraf uchun quyidagi oddiy sonli differensiallash protsedurasini qo'llashimiz mumkin:

$$\eta^{j+1} = \frac{m}{f_0} \frac{\theta^{j+1} - \theta^j}{\tau}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (18)$$

Qaralayotgan oshkormas sxemani realizatsiya qilish uchun to'rtli masalani yechish muammosiga alohida to'xtalish zarur.

4. To'rtli nolokal masala va uni realizatsiya qilish

(14)-(16) sxema bo'yicha hisoblashni realizatsiya qilish hech qanday maxsus muammo tug'dirmaydi, to'rtli masalaning nostandartligiga (nolokalligiga) qaramasdan yangi vaqt qatlamida hech qanday muammo paydo bo'lmaydi. (14) tenglama ichki tugunlarda quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi

$$\frac{w_i^{j+1}}{\tau} + \frac{v}{m} \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2h} - \frac{D}{m} \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - 2w_i^{j+1} + w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h^2} + \frac{1}{m\psi_k} w_k^{j+1} (D(\psi''_{xx})_i - v(\psi'_x)_i) = g_i^j, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (19)$$

bu yerda $g_i^j = \frac{w_i^j}{\tau} + \frac{1}{m\psi_k} \varphi^{j+1} (D(\psi''_{xx})_i - v(\psi'_x)_i)$. (19) tenglama uchun chegaraviy

shart (15) bo'ladi. (15), (19) sistema yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishda izlanadi

$$w_i^{j+1} = y_i + w_k^{j+1} z_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N. \quad (20)$$

(20) ni (19) ga qo'yib y_i, z_i yordamchi funksiyalar uchun quyidagi to'rtli masalani hosil qilamiz

$$\frac{y_i}{\tau} + \frac{v}{m} \frac{y_{i+1} - y_{i-1}}{2h} - \frac{D}{m} \frac{y_{i+1} - 2y_i + y_{i-1}}{h^2} = g_i^j, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad (21)$$

$$y_0 = c_0, \quad y_N = 0, \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{z_i}{\tau} + \frac{v}{m} \frac{z_{i+1} - z_{i-1}}{2h} - \frac{D}{m} \frac{z_{i+1} - 2z_i + z_{i-1}}{h^2} + \frac{1}{m\psi_k} (D(\psi''_{xx})_i - v(\psi'_x)_i) = 0, \quad (23)$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1,$$

$$z_0 = 0, \quad z_N = 0. \quad (24)$$

Shundan keyin (20) ni hisobga olib w_k^{j+1} ni topamiz:

$$w_k^{j+1} = \frac{y_k}{1 - z_k}. \quad (25)$$

Algoritmning korrektiligini (25) ning maxraji nolga aylanmasligi ta'minlaydi.

(21), (22) va (23), (24) to'rtli masalalar standart masalalar hisoblanadi va ularni sonli yechish hech qanday qiyinchilik tug'dirmaydi.

(21), (23) tenglamalar quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$Ay_{i-1} - Cy_i + By_{i+1} = -F_i^j, \quad (26)$$

$$Az_{i-1} - Cz_i + Bz_{i+1} = -\bar{F}_i^j, \quad (27)$$

bu yerda

$$A = \frac{D\tau}{mh^2} + \frac{v\tau}{2mh}, \quad B = \frac{D\tau}{mh^2} - \frac{v\tau}{2mh}, \quad C = \frac{2D\tau}{mh^2} + 1,$$

$$F_i^j = \tau g_i^j, \quad \bar{F}_i^j = \frac{\tau}{m\psi_k} (v(\psi'_x)_i - D(\psi''_{xx})_i).$$

(22), (26) chegaraviy masalani progonka usuli yordamida yechish algoritmi quyida ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$y_i = \alpha_{i+1}y_{i+1} + \beta_{i+1}, \quad i = N-1, N-2, \dots, 1, 0, \quad (28)$$

$$\alpha_{i+1} = \frac{B}{C - A\alpha_i}, \quad \beta_{i+1} = \frac{A\beta_i + F_i^j}{C - A\alpha_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad (29)$$

$$y_0 = \alpha_1 y_1 + \beta_1 = c_0, \quad \alpha_1 = 0, \quad \beta_1 = c_0, \quad (30)$$

$$y_N = 0. \quad (31)$$

Endi (24), (27) chegaraviy masalaning ham progonka usuli yordamida yechish algoritmini keltiramiz:

$$z_i = \bar{\alpha}_{i+1}z_{i+1} + \bar{\beta}_{i+1}, \quad i = N-1, N-2, \dots, 1, 0, \quad (32)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_{i+1} = \frac{B}{C - A\bar{\alpha}_i}, \quad \bar{\beta}_{i+1} = \frac{A\bar{\beta}_i + \bar{F}_i^j}{C - A\bar{\alpha}_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad (33)$$

$$z_0 = \bar{\alpha}_1 z_1 + \bar{\beta}_1 = 0, \quad \bar{\alpha}_1 = 0, \quad \bar{\beta}_1 = 0, \quad (34)$$

$$z_N = 0. \quad (35)$$

Kvazireal eksperiment o'tkazish qandaydir o'ng taraf bilan berilgan (1)-(3) to'g'ri masala qaraladi. O'ng taraf (4) munosabat beriladi, bu yerda

$$\psi(x) = \sin \frac{\pi x}{l}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq l,$$

$$\eta(t) = \begin{cases} t, & 0 < t < 0,6T, \\ 0, & 0,6T < t < T. \end{cases}$$

Teskari masalani yechishda $\varphi(t)$ to'r funksiya tasodifiy xatoliklar bilan quyidagicha modellashtiriladi [6, 19]

$$\varphi_\delta^j = \varphi^j + 2\delta(\sigma^j - 0,5), \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M,$$

bu yerda σ^j - tasodifiy funksiya bo'lib $[0,1]$ kesmada tekis taqsimlangan sonlarni beradi. δ kattalik xatolik darajasini beradi. 1-rasmda $\varphi(t)$ funksiyaning grafigi $\delta = 0$ da tasvirlangan.

1-rasm. $\varphi(t)$ funksiyaning grafigi ($\delta = 0$ da)

2-7-rasmlarda $\eta(t)$ tiklanishi bo'yicha sonli natijalari tasvirlangan. 2-rasmda $\delta = 0$ da tiklangan $\eta(t)$ funksiya aniq $\eta(t)$ funksiya bilan ustma-ust tushganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. 3-7 rasmlarda $\varphi(t)$ funksiya mos ravishda $\delta = 0,00001; 0,00005; 0,0001; 0,00025; 0,0005$ xatoliklar bilan berilgandagi $\eta(t)$ funksiyaning tiklanish grafiglari berilgan.

2-rasm. $\delta = 0$ da $\eta(t)$ funksiyaning tiklanishi

3-rasm. $\delta = 0,00001$ da $\eta(t)$ funksiyaning tiklanishi

4-rasm. $\delta = 0,00005$ da $\eta(t)$ funksiyaning tiklanishi

5-rasm. $\delta = 0,0001$ da $\eta(t)$ funksiyaning tiklanishi

6-rasm. $\delta = 0,00025$ da $\eta(t)$ funksiyaning tiklanishi

7-rasm. $\delta = 0,0005$ da $\eta(t)$ funksiyaning tiklanishi

3-4 rasmlardagi sonli natijalardan ko'rinib turibdiki, δ xatolik darajasining kichik qiymatlarida $\eta(t)$ tiklanishini amalda qo'llash mumkin. Ammo δ ning kattaroq qiymatlarida $\eta(t)$ o'ng taraf funksiyasining tiklanishi turg'unmas xarakterga ega (5-7 rasmlar). Bundan ko'rinadiki o'ng tarafni tiklash masalasida yechim haqidagi qo'shimcha ma'lumotlar ($\varphi(t)$ funksiya) xatoligi ma'lum darajadan oshib ketmasligi kerak ekan.

ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Тихонов А. Арсенин В. Я. Методы решения некорректных задач. М.: Наука, 1986.
2. Лаврентьев М. Л., Романов В. Г., Шишатский С. П. Некорректные задачи математической физики. М.: Наука, 1980.
3. Алифанов О. М. Обратные задачи теплообмена. М.: Машиностроение, 1988.
4. Алифанов О. Л., Артюхин Е.А., Румянцев С. В. Экстремальные методы решения некорректных задач. М.: Наука, 1988.
5. Кабанихин С. И. Обратные и некорректные задачи. Учебник для студентов высших учебных заведений. — Новосибирск: Сибирское научное издательство, 2009. — 457 с.
6. Самарский А. А., Вабнщевич П. Н. Численные методы решения обратных задач математической физики: Учебное пособие. Изд. 3-е. — М.: Издательство ЛКИ, 2009. — 480 с.
7. Khuzhayorov B.Kh, Kholiyarov É.Ch. Inverse problems of elastoplastic filtration of liquid in a porous medium // Journal of Engineering Physics and Thermophysics 80 (3), 517-525.

8. Khuzhayorov, B. K., Ali, F. M., Sulaymonov, F. U., & Kholiyarov, E. C. (2016, June). Inverse coefficient problem for mass transfer in two-zone cylindrical porous medium. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 1739, No. 1, p. 020028). AIP Publishing LLC.
9. Khuzhayorov B. K., Kholiyarov E. C., Shodmonkulov M. T. AN INVERSE COEFFICIENT PROBLEM FOR A NONLINEAR PARABOLIC EQUATION // ПРИКЛАДНОЙ И ГЕОМЕТРИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ. – 2014. – С. 18-18.
10. Khuzhayorov B. K., Kholiyarov E. C., Mamatov S. Identification of the coefficients of relaxation filtration of a homogeneous liquid in porous media // *AIP Conference Proceedings*. – AIP Publishing LLC, 2022. – Т. 2637. – №. 1. – С. 040009.
11. Kholiyarov, E. C., Ernazarov, M. Y., Jurayev, O. A., & Abdurazzokov, J. R. (2022, October). Coefficient inverse problem for a simplified model of filtration of a homogeneous fluid in fractured-porous medium. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2637, No. 1, p. 040021). AIP Publishing LLC.
12. Normurodov, C., Kholiyarov, E., Gulomkodiroy, K., & Djurayeva, N. (2022, October). Numerical simulation of the inverse problem for the vortex-current equation. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2637, No. 1, p. 040018). AIP Publishing LLC.
13. Khuzhayorov B., Begmatov T., Kholiyarov E., Fayziev B. The inverse problem of determining the kinetic coefficients in the model of suspension filtration in a porous medium // *Eurasian journal of mathematical and computer applications*. Volume 10, Issue 4 (2022) 96 -106.
14. Бегматов Т. И., Холияров Э. Ч., Файзиев Б. М. Идентификация коэффициента кинетики в модели фильтрации суспензии в пористой среде // *Проблемы вычислительной и прикладной математики*. Т. 38, №1, С. 9-16.
15. Kholiyarov E., Shadmonov I., Sherpulatov Sh. Identification of the flow coefficient in a truncated model of fluid filtration in fractured-porous media // *Austrian Journal of Technical and Natural Sciences*, 2022. №1-2, P. 8-12.
16. Холияров Э. Ч., Шадманов И. Э., Шерпулатов Ш. Ш. Определение коэффициента перетока в модели фильтрации уоррена-рута на основе решения обратной задаче // *Universum: технические науки*. – 2022. – №. 5-2 (98). – С. 51-58.
17. Holyarov E., Makhmudov T. D. Inverse problems of elastic-plastic filtration of liquid in homogeneous layers // *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 04 (84). – 2020. – С. 242-251.
18. Хужаёров Б. Х., Холияров Э. Ч. Проблемы вычислительной и прикладной математики // *Проблемы вычислительной и прикладной математики*. – №. 1. – С. 66-76.
19. Вабищевич П.Н. Численное решение задачи идентификации правой части параболического уравнения. *Изв. вузов. Матем.*, 2003, 1, 29 –37.

20. Борухов В.Т., Вабищевич П.Н. Численное решение обратной задачи восстановления источника в параболическом уравнении, *Матем. моделирование*, **10:11** (1998), 93–100.
21. Bear J. Dynamics of fluids in porous media. American Elsevier Publishing Co., New York. 1972. – 764 p.
22. Самарский А.А. Теория разностных схем. М.: Наука, 1983. – 616 с.